

PREDICTION OF KIDNEY TRANSPLANTATION INFECTION BASED ON TRADITIONAL MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Infection prediction after kidney transplantation is significant. Most existing models for predicting kidney transplant infection are statistical, unintelligent, and straightforward. The foremost task of this paper is to analyze kidney transplantation data, introduce existing traditional machine learning and deep learning methods from non-temporal and temporal scenarios, respectively, and comprehensively evaluate the predictive power of the methods for kidney transplantation infection. Specifically, in the non-temporal scenario, we use Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbor, Support Vector Machines, and Random Forest models. In addition, in the temporal scenario, we propose an MTAN model based on a sliding window algorithm to exploit the hidden information of adjacent time series fully. Experimental results show that the kidney transplantation prediction models built by Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machines have better stability than those constructed by K-Nearest Neighbor and Random Forest. The MTAN model with sliding windows can better mine the hidden temporal information.

KEYWORDS

Kidney Transplant Infection Prediction, Traditional Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Sliding Window

1. INTRODUCTION

With the improvement of the medical level and the emergence of advanced medical equipment, patients' terminal renal disease can already be effectively treated by kidney transplantation. Patients may have postoperative infections and other complications after renal transplantation [1], which will seriously affect the graft's survival rate and the recipient's survival rate. Consequently, doctors must arrange irregular and variable laboratory tests for patients and monitor their physical conditions according to the laboratory results and clinical manifestations so that any infection can be detected promptly. Hospitals use advanced electronic health systems to record patients' postoperative laboratory results and diagnostic reports, mostly imbalanced, irregular, and multivariate data with missing values. Moreover, the number of laboratory results and diagnostic

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reports increases as the number of tests increases. A kidney transplant infection prediction model is therefore essential to best use the patient's laboratory information and provide accurate predictions for the physician's diagnosis, which will alleviate the strained medical resources.

With the development of technologies such as natural language processing, computer vision, and data mining, the integration of artificial intelligence technology with the medical and healthcare sector is deepening, and the medical application scenarios are becoming more prosperous. The main application scenarios are text analysis of medical records, medical image-assisted diagnosis, drug development, intelligent dialogue robot, intelligent logistics robot, and intelligent analysis of individualized medical data. Regarding the intelligent analysis of individualized medical data, there are many large public medical datasets for scholars to study. Using artificial intelligence algorithms to solve medical data classification problems has become a more common solution.

This paper is an engineering exercise for kidney transplant data analysis, aiming to introduce existing traditional machine learning and deep learning methods to the task and to evaluate each type of method's performance comprehensively. It is challenging to construct a kidney transplant infection prediction model because our kidney transplant dataset is unbalanced, irregular, sparse, multivariate data with single time step prediction, there is no publicly available medical dataset with the same characteristics for the time being, and the task of kidney transplant infection prediction is less studied in the field of artificial intelligence. Compared with other studies on kidney transplant infection prediction in Section 2, our contributions are: 1) we analyze the kidney transplant dataset under non-temporal scenarios and temporal scenarios, respectively. 2) we build a traditional machine learning-based kidney transplant infection prediction model under non-temporal scenarios, in which we use Naive Bayes, K-nearest Neighbor, Support Vector Machines, and Random Forest models as baseline models, in addition, we explore the effects of imbalanced datasets and feature selection on the classification of Naïve Bayes, K-nearest Neighbour, Support Vector Machines and Random Forest.3) In the temporal scenario, we propose a sliding window-based MTAN kidney transplant infection prediction model in a temporal scenario and explore the effects of imbalanced datasets and sliding windows on the classification of the MTAN model.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we present research related to kidney transplant infection prediction. In Section 3, we present relevant traditional machine learning and deep learning approaches, as well as system architectures for non-temporal scenarios and temporal scenarios. In Section 4, we present the kidney transplant dataset and analyze and evaluate kidney transplant prediction models in that section. Finally, we conclude the performance of the kidney transplant infection prediction model in non-temporal and temporal scenarios in Section 5 and discuss the shortcomings of the kidney transplant infection prediction model and future research directions for improvement in Section 6.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on the prediction of kidney transplant infection has focused on the medical field. In [2], Lochmanova et al. used Quantiferon-CMV assay to predict cytomegalovirus infection after renal transplant. According to Marta's research, they monitored pretransplant CMV-specific cell-mediated immunity using an interferon- γ release assay to predict CMV infection in kidney transplantation [3]. These methods of infection prediction are achieved through medical tests as well as statistics in a simple way, without even using models. Among the models for predicting kidney transplant infection, the most common is the COX proportional risk model, a statistical method. Pérez-Jacoiste adopted univariate and multivariate Cox proportional risk models to research the intracellular concentrations of adenosine triphosphate to predict infection after kidney transplantation [4]. In [5], Zhou et al. used a COX proportional risk model to analyze the

effect of ABCB1 gene polymorphisms on infection in kidney transplant recipients taking tacrolimus after surgery. These researchers above are still based on statistical studies and do not use artificial intelligence to address the problem of kidney transplant infection prediction.

There are few studies on infection prediction after kidney transplantation in artificial intelligence, and logistic regression model prediction is commonly used. Wang et al. used logistic regression to investigate the predictive value of tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), interleukin-10 (IL-10), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin-2 (IL-2), and interleukin-8 (IL-8) on postoperative infection in kidney transplant patients [6]. Gon et al. used multivariate logistic regression analysis to build risk prediction models and analyze pulmonary infection's occurrence and risk factors after renal transplantation [7]. The above studies were conducted on relatively balanced small sample datasets with different distributions from real kidney transplant datasets and using simple methods that do not allow deeper mining of kidney transplant data, so it is of great interest to analyze and model large, real kidney transplant datasets based on traditional machine learning and deep learning.

3. METHODOLOGY

As the kidney transplant data are numerical and carries temporal information, we can use traditional machine learning to predict when the temporal information is ignored; otherwise, we use deep learning to predict. Before presenting two systematic frameworks for kidney transplant infection prediction, we will briefly introduce the relevant theoretical foundations of traditional machine learning and deep learning.

3.1. Traditional Machine Learning Methods for Analyzing the Kidney Transplant Dataset

Traditional machine learning is well suited to the analysis and prediction of numerical data. The standard process is to analyze and process the data first and then model it with traditional machine models. Therefore, we first briefly describe the method of addressing the imbalanced dataset and the feature selection methods before presenting the traditional machine models used in the paper.

3.1.1. Methods for Imbalanced Dataset

Real-world healthcare datasets generally suffer from an imbalanced distribution of datasets. When the ratio of positive and negative samples in the dataset is imbalanced, two perspectives usually solve it: data-level and algorithm-level [8]. From the data-level perspective, the primary methods are oversampling and undersampling. Oversampling method supplements the imbalanced dataset directly by generating minority-class samples. By contrast, undersampling has balanced the dataset by discarding majority-class samples, suffering from the loss of information. To minimize the loss of information, we can use an optimized under-sampling algorithm, EasyEnsemble [9], which is an integration method to retain as majority-class samples as possible. This paper uses the SMOTE oversampling, undersampling, and EasyEnsemble methods to process the imbalanced kidney transplant dataset.

3.1.2. Feature Selection

Feature selection aims to reduce feature space dimensionality and improve machine learning performance by retaining useful features and removing irrelevant and redundant features. As our dataset has multiple features, we first need to select the efficacious features to supply the model for training to improve the model's generalization performance.

Feature selection methods can be broadly classified into wrapped, filtered, and embedded methods according to the selection strategy [10]. The commonly used wrapped method is the REFCV method. The REFCV method is to first get the combination of all feature subsets by the search strategy. Then the model evaluates the quality of the feature subsets to find the optimal feature subsets. The commonly used filtered methods are the Pearson correlation coefficient for normally distributed data, the Spearman correlation coefficient for monotonic data, and the Kendall correlation coefficient for ordered data [11], which are used for feature selection by analyzing the correlation of features. A commonly used embedded method is the L1 regularization method, which is often put into the loss function calculation of the model. In this paper, we use these methods to select features in an integrated way.

3.1.3. Naïve Bayes

Based on Bayes' theorem, Naïve Bayes (NB) was proposed. It is a simple and effective classifier that relies on the assumption of conditional independence of features[12].

The feature conditional independence assumption, namely, the individual feature is unrelated to each other so that the multivariate problem can degrade to a set of univariate problems. Equation (1) indicates the conditional probability distribution, where x_i denotes the i -th feature and y_j denotes the j -th category. When given the target value y_j , the conditional probability $P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n | y_j)$ of joint features is the product of the conditional probabilities of the independent occurrence of each feature.

$$P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n | y_j) = \prod_i P(x_i | y_j) \quad (1)$$

$$P(y_j | x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{P(y_j) \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i | y_j)}{\prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i)} \quad (2)$$

The basic process of classification by the NB algorithm is: firstly, calculate the probability of occurrence of each category $P(y_j)$ based on the preprocessed data, then estimate the conditional probability $P(x_i | y_j)$ of occurrence of each feature under each category, later estimate the probability $P(y_j | x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ corresponding to each category after combining features, as shown in Equation (2). Finally, the maximum category probability corresponding to the combination of features is selected as the inference result.

3.1.4. K- Nearest Neighbor

Cover and Hart initially proposed the K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), an inert algorithm, in 1968 [13]. The basic process of the KNN algorithm is: by calculating the distance between the new sample to be tested and each sample point in the training set, the classification result of the first K samples with the smallest distance is selected as the classification reference of the test sample, and then the algorithm will recommend the category with the highest frequency as the

classification of the test sample, where the distance is often expressed as Euclidean distance, and the formula of Euclidean distance between two points is represented as follows.

$$\rho = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2} \tag{3}$$

3.1.5. Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machine (SVM) aims to construct a hyperplane to separate different categories of data on opposite sides. As the points on either side of the hyperplane are further away from the hyperplane, the better the classification will be. We need to find an optimal separating hyperplane so that the points on the dataset are as far away from the hyperplane as possible. The expression of the hyperplane is shown in Equation (4), and the two-dimensional space hyperplane is a line.

$$w^T x + b = 0 \tag{4}$$

Kernel function, penalty factor C, and kernel function parameter gamma are significant parameters of the SVM. Grid search and cross-validation can assist penalty factor and kernel function parameters in finding the optimal solution and eliminating training bias to ensure the generalization ability of Support Vector Machine.

Figure 1. Random Forest algorithm

3.1.6. Random Forest

Random Forest (RF) is an algorithm in which weak classifiers are integrated by bagging into an upgraded, robust classifier. In practice, the randomness of Random Forest lies in the selection of samples and features. More specifically, randomness refers that each decision tree has randomly selected n retrievable samples in the training set and randomly selected m features for learning.

The basic process of RF algorithm is as follows: initially construct N decision trees, and each tree randomly selected n retrievable samples and m features, then all decision trees engage in classification to get their individual classification results, and finally take the plurality of the

classification results of all decision trees as the classification result of Random Forest. The classification process for RF is shown in Figure 1.

3.2. System Architecture for Non-Temporal Scenarios

Since the kidney transplantation dataset is composed of continuous numerical data, the data are independent of each other in the non-temporal scenario after ignoring the temporal features, thus, which can be directly modeled by traditional machine learning methods. The system architecture is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. System architecture for non-temporal scenarios

The original kidney transplant dataset has invalid data, so the dataset needs to be cleaned first. As the proportion of positive and negative samples in the dataset is imbalanced, we need to balance the dataset subsequently and use feature selection to extract useful features and reduce the dimensionality of the feature space. After processing the kidney transplant dataset, we use NB, KNN, SVM, and RF as baseline models to construct the kidney transplant infection prediction models.

3.3. Deep Learning Methods for Analyzing the Kidney Transplant Dataset

Deep learning is divided into two main categories: convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks. In detail, convolutional neural networks mainly handle image problems, and recurrent neural networks mainly solve time series problems. To predict the time series, recurrent neural networks also need to analyze and process the data before modeling the time series.

3.3.1. Under Sampling

We sort the kidney transplant dataset into time series in the temporal scenario. However, the time series dataset is still imbalanced, which means an imbalance exists between and within the time series. The imbalance within the time series is because our data are labeled at each point in time. To slightly balance the time series dataset, we discard ones that do not contain positive samples, so we only need to focus on the imbalance within the time series later.

3.3.2. Sliding Window Method

The sliding window method is one of the essential methods of data partitioning that can be used to solve sub-element problems of arrays or strings, which can reduce the time complexity. We can use the sliding window method to segment a long time series in the kidney transplant dataset into multiple short time series, and then use the time series model to extract the key patterns present in the non-periodic time series to improve the efficiency of data analysis and to further solve the problem of imbalance within the time series.

When processing time series data with the sliding window method, three things should be noted: the direction, the length, and the step size of the sliding window.

3.3.3. MTAN

MTAN (Multi-Time Attention Networks) is a deep learning framework proposed by Shukla [14] et al. for multivariate, irregular, and temporal data with missing values, divided into two parts: the encoder and the decoder. We only use the encoder part for the classification of time series. The encoder part of the MTAN is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The architecture of the MTAN-encoder

MTAN improves the problem that position encoding in the transformer model [15] can only solve discrete positions inputs by introducing a learnable time embedding, so MATN can take continuous time as an input [14]. The i -dimensional embedding h at continuous time point t is defined as follows:

$$\phi_h(t)[i] = \begin{cases} \omega_{0h} \cdot t + \alpha_{0h}, & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \sin(\omega_{ih} \cdot t + \alpha_{ih}), & \text{if } 0 < i < d_r \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where the ω_{ih} and α_{ih} are learnable parameters. The sinusoidal function term captures the periodicity in the time series, and conversely, the linear term captures the non-periodicity in the time series.

The multi-time attention mechanism takes t and \mathbf{s} as input, where t is a query time point and \mathbf{s} is a multivariate, sparse, and irregular time series with D dimensions and the multi-time attention mechanism outputs a j dimensional embedding representation $mTAN(t, \mathbf{s})[j]$. As shown in Equation (6) and Equation (7), $mTAN(t, \mathbf{s})[j]$ is formed by the linear combination $\hat{x}_{hd}(t, \mathbf{s})$ which is a smoother kernel, and the parameters U_{hdj} are learnable weights. $K_h(t, t_{id})$ is the interpolation weights defined in Equation (8). $K_h(t, t_{id})$ is calculated from the time embedding of the query time t and the time embedding of the observation time t_{id} based on the attention mechanism.

Since the final output of the mTAN module cannot be directly merged into a neural network architecture that requires takes fixed dimensional vectors or discrete sequences as inputs, a further transformation is required. The output representation can be computed according to a collection of reference time points \mathbf{r} , with a fixed length output computed through an attention mechanism. Finally, the module takes a linear combination of multivariate output representations as output. This complete module is referred to as MTAND and is shown in Figure 4.

$$mTAN(t, \mathbf{s})[j] = \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{d=1}^D \hat{x}_{hd}(t, \mathbf{s}) \cdot U_{hdj} \tag{6}$$

$$\hat{x}_{hd}(t, \mathbf{s}) = \sum_{i=1}^{L_d} K_h(t, t_{id}) x_{id} \tag{7}$$

$$K_h(t, t_{id}) = \frac{\exp(\phi_h(t) \mathbf{w} \mathbf{v}^T \phi_h(t_{id})^T / \sqrt{d_k})}{\sum_{i'=1}^{L_d} \exp(\phi_h(t) \mathbf{w} \mathbf{v}^T \phi_h(t_{i'd})^T / \sqrt{d_k})} \tag{8}$$

Figure 4. The architecture of the mTAND module

3.4. System Architecture for Temporal Scenarios

In the actual diagnosis scenario, the doctor needs to combine the current laboratory results with the previous laboratory results and diagnosis results to give the diagnosis, so the kidney transplant data are time-series data. As the time intervals of the patient’s laboratory tests are closely related to the change in the patient’s physical condition, time intervals mean a lot. Under the temporal scenario, the kidney transplantation dataset has the characteristics of irregular, multivariate, imbalanced, sparse, and single time-step classification. After the study, we conclusively selected the MTAN model for predicting infection, and the system architecture is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. System architecture for temporal scenarios

Like traditional machine learning, we need first to clean the dataset and solve the imbalanced dataset problem. Subsequently, the sliding window approach partitions the time series into small time segments, which MATN takes as inputs. Finally, we use the MTAN model to predict kidney transplant infection.

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1. Kidney Transplant Dataset

The kidney transplant dataset used in this paper is from the Third Medical Center of the General Hospital of the Chinese People's Liberation Army, which was collected from 2016 to 2019, with basic information, physiological variables, and diagnostic results of desensitized 1890 patients. More specifically, the basic information includes the ID, age, and gender of the desensitized patients. The physiological variables consist of multivariate time series data with 15 variables, such as LYM, CD3, CD3/L, et al. The diagnostic results were divided into infected and uninfected, with 15,373 infected data and 468 uninfected data. 2.95% of the records have positive labels. In the kidney transplant dataset, records of the same patient contain sparse and irregularly spaced measurements. In addition, the number of records is variable for each patient, ranging from 1 to 51. After data cleaning, 15841 valid data are available for the study. The local Clinical Research Ethics Committee approved the study protocol (Ethical Review Scientific No. KY2021-033), and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

4.2. Experimental Setup

4.2.1. Dataset Partition

The dataset is first cleaned to remove invalid data, symbols, and values. Then, we group the dataset by patient ID. Later, we randomly divide the dataset into a training set containing 80% of the instances, a validation set containing 10%, and a test set containing 10% of instances. In addition, the same patient ID will only appear in one data set among the training, validation, and test set. The non-temporal and temporal scenarios use the same training, validation, and test sets, but the temporal scenario organizes the data further into time series.

4.2.2. Performance Metrics

In this paper, we assess performance using accuracy, the area under the ROC curve (AUROC), recall, and F1 score, which we can use the confusion matrix to deduce. Moreover, the ROC curve is plotted with the false positive rate (FPR) as the horizontal coordinate and the true positive Rate (TPR) as the vertical coordinate. The performance metrics are defined as follows:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (9)$$

$$Recall = TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (10)$$

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (11)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (12)$$

$$F1 = \frac{2 * Recall * Precision}{Recall + Precision} \quad (13)$$

where TP-true positive, TN-true negative, FP-false positive, FN-false negative.

4.2.3. Model Parameters

In the KNN model, the `n_neighbors` parameter is set to 5. In the SVM model, the `C` and `gamma` parameters are both set to 0.001. The MTAN model is trained for 500 epochs using the Adam optimizer, with an initial learning rate equal to 0.001. We set the batch normalization to 64. Moreover, we set the length of the sliding window to 6 and the step to 6.

4.3. Results

4.3.1. Results of Feature Selection for the Kidney Transplant Dataset

The results of the feature selection for all methods are shown in Table 1. Figure 6 shows NK/LYM and B/LYM are duplicate features with a correlation coefficient of 1. Thus, we cannot keep them both. In addition, we can also learn that there is a strong correlation between CD4/L and CD4/3, CD3 and CD8 counts, CD8/L and CD8/CD3, and B/LYM and B cells.

Figure 6. The correlation analysis of the features

Table 1. The result of the feature selection.

Method	Results of the Feature Selection (ranked in the top six)
REFCV	CD3, CD4count, CD4/L, CD8/L, Bcell, NKcell
Pearson correlation coefficient	CD4/CD8, CD4/L, CD4/3, B/LYM, NK/LYM, CD3/L
Spearman correlation coefficient	CD4/3, CD4/CD8, CD4/L, CD3/L, B/LYM, Bcell
Kendall correlation coefficient	CD4/3, CD4/CD8, CD4/L, CD3/L, B/LYM, Bcell
L1 regularization	CD3, CD4count, CD4/3, CD8count, CD8/CD3, Bcell

Consequently, based on the combined consideration of the selection results of the three feature selection methods of wrapped, filtered, and embedded and the correlation analysis of features, six crucial features are selected: CD3, CD4 count, CD4/L, CD8/L, B cells, and NK cell.

4.3.2. Results of Kidney Transplantation Prediction for Non-Temporal Scenarios

In the non-temporal scenario, the accuracy, AUROC, recall, and f1 score of each model on the test set are recorded to compare the classification performance of NB, KNN, SVM, and RF on the kidney transplant dataset, as well as to explore the effect of different balanced dataset approaches and feature selection on model prediction. We are focusing on the ability of the models to classify positive samples, and the results are shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2. Comparison of the traditional machine learning models under different methods to balance dataset.

Methods	Model	Accuracy(%)	AUROC(%)	Recall(%)	F1(%)
Original	NB	95.49	65	6.06	5.56
	KNN	97.54	52	0	0
	SVM	97.81	52	0	0
	RF	97.28	61	0	0
SMOTE oversampling	NB	48.97	68	75.76	6.11
	KNN	81.82	60	33.33	7.43
	SVM	74.75	74	63.64	9.84
	RF	93.30	62	24.24	13.7
Undersampling	NB	57.53	69	72.73	6.98
	KNN	69.61	65	51.52	6.91
	SVM	68.94	72	60.61	7.87
	RF	76.05	68	57.58	9.52
Easyensemble	NB	73.06	65	51.52	7.73
	KNN	70.14	67	51.52	7.02
	SVM	70.80	71	60.61	8.33
	RF	74.12	66	57.58	8.88

Table 2 shows that each model trained under the original dataset has almost no ability to predict positive samples correctly, although the prediction accuracy is high. The three balanced dataset approaches significantly improve the AUROC, recall, and F1 score of each model. Differences in performance metrics and models make it difficult to compare methods directly, and different methods of balancing datasets have different effects on different models. Taking the NB model as an example, the SMOTE balanced dataset gives the model the best prediction for positive samples. However, the generation of SMOTE may introduce some noise or generate too similar samples, leading to KNN and RF overfitting. Since we only solve the imbalance problem in the training set, the test set still maintains the original highly imbalanced distribution. The models enhance the classification ability of positive samples and improve recall. It is also because of the change in the training set distribution that the models all get low f1 scores when tested on the test set of the original distribution, and the models become less capable of classifying negative samples, indicating that the generalization ability of the models is insufficient.

Table 3. Comparison of the traditional machine learning models under different methods to balance dataset after feature selection.

Methods	Model	Accuracy(%)	AUROC(%)	Recall(%)	F1(%)
Original	NB	97.74	68	0	0
	KNN	97.68	49	0	0
	SVM	97.81	38	0	0
	RF	97.54	57	6.06	9.76
SMOTE oversampling	NB	60.05	70	66.67	6.81
	KNN	79.10	51	15.15	3.08
	SVM	72.99	73	60.61	8.94
	RF	92.90	63	15.15	8.55
Undersampling	NB	67.62	69	63.64	7.92
	KNN	67.02	65	54.55	6.75
	SVM	70.60	71	60.61	8.28
	RF	76.11	61	45.45	7.69
Easyensemble	NB	66.03	68	66.67	7.91
	KNN	69.08	67	57.58	7.54
	SVM	70.80	71	60.61	8.33
	RF	73.52	66	60.61	9.11

A comparison of Table 2 and Table 3 shows that feature selection affects each model differently and is influenced by data distribution and data size. Feature selection may not improve the performance of the models. However, for the Easy Ensemble balanced dataset, feature selection improves the individual models' AUROC, recall, and F1 scores. Finally, on balance, NB and SVM are more effective and relatively more stable in classifying positive samples among the traditional machine learning models used in this paper.

4.3.3. Results of Kidney Transplantation Prediction for Temporal Scenarios

In the temporal scenario, the accuracy, AUROC, recall, and F1 scores of the MTAN temporal model on the test set are recorded to measure the model's performance on the kidney transplant dataset and to explore the effects of under sampling and the sliding window methods. As with the non-temporal scenarios, we remain more interested in the model's predictive ability on positive samples, and the results are presented in Table 4.

When the dataset is imbalanced, the prediction ability of MTAN for positive samples is 0. After undersampling the time-series kidney transplant dataset, the recall is increased by 30%, and the prediction performance for positive samples is significantly improved. The introduction of the sliding window further balances the dataset, which exploits the hidden information of positive samples in the time series, thus the recall of the model classification is increased by 35%, and at the same time, the F1 score increases by 1.13%. Compared to traditional machine learning models, the temporal MTAN model has higher accuracy and AUROC but lower F1 scores with essentially the same maximum recall. On further analysis, the reason for the low F1 score is that there are more cases where negative samples are predicted as positive samples since the undersampling discards the negative-only time series, resulting in the model not learning enough about the negative-only time series. From the classification results, both the undersampling and sliding window methods effectively improved the classification accuracy of the MTAN model for positive samples. The sliding window was beneficial in helping the MATN model to dig deeper into the hidden information of the positive sample time series. However, the MTAN model performed poorly as the processed dataset was still internally imbalanced, with 14.3% of positive samples in each time series. In addition, the positive samples are discontinuous in terms of time steps, so it is difficult for the MTAN model to mine the positive samples' hidden information

entirely. If we want to use the temporal information better, we need to delve further into the time series data and the MTAN model.

Table 4. Comparison of MTAN models on different methods.

Methods	Accuracy(%)	AUROC(%)	Recall(%)	F1(%)
Original	99.54	31.08	0	0
Undersampling	91.41	72.86	30	3.11
Undersampling+Sliding window	86.51	78.35	65	4.24

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper uses existing traditional machine learning and deep learning models to design kidney transplant infection prediction models in non-temporal and temporal scenarios, respectively. In the non-temporal scenario, the kidney transplantation prediction models constructed based on Naïve Bayes, KNN, Support Vector Machine, and Random Forest have better classification performance on the balanced dataset, among which the kidney transplantation prediction models constructed by Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machine are more stable. The balanced dataset can significantly improve the infection prediction ability of the MTAN-based kidney transplant infection prediction model in the time-series scenario. In addition, the sliding window method can further improve the ability of MTAN to mine temporal information, thus improving the accuracy of positive classification.

6. DISCUSSION

In the temporal scenario, we discard the time series with negative-only samples to balance the dataset, which leads to the poor prediction of the kidney transplant infection prediction model for negative samples. In the future, we will continue to improve the method to deal with the imbalance, save more time series information, and improve the kidney transplant infection prediction model from the time series generation or model integration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We gratefully acknowledge the support by the organ transplantation department of the Third Medical Center of the General Hospital of the Chinese People's Liberation Army for providing the kidney transplant dataset. This work was also supported by Innovation and Transformation Fund of Peking University Third Hospital (No.BYSYZHKC2021115).

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